

SENOVIE - NCC Breast Cancer Registry

Patient form

Patient (patient form)

NCC Patient Nb.	
First names	
Family name	
Sex	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Male <input type="checkbox"/> (2) Female <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Birth date	__ / __ / ____ (DD/MM/YYYY)
Birth place	Province/City: Srok/Khan: Khum/Sangkat:
Telephone	
Ethnic	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Khmer <input type="checkbox"/> (2) Chinese <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Vietnamese <input type="checkbox"/> (4) Cham <input type="checkbox"/> (5) Other <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Occupation	<input type="checkbox"/> (01) Accountant <input type="checkbox"/> (02) Agriculture <input type="checkbox"/> (03) Businessman <input type="checkbox"/> (04) Chef <input type="checkbox"/> (05) Consultant <input type="checkbox"/> (06) Doctor <input type="checkbox"/> (07) Driver <input type="checkbox"/> (08) Electrician <input type="checkbox"/> (09) Engineer <input type="checkbox"/> (10) Engineering technologist <input type="checkbox"/> (11) Factory worker <input type="checkbox"/> (12) Farmer <input type="checkbox"/> (13) Government officer/Employee <input type="checkbox"/> (14) Hairdresser <input type="checkbox"/> (15) Housewife <input type="checkbox"/> (16) IT <input type="checkbox"/> (17) Laborer <input type="checkbox"/> (18) Lawyer <input type="checkbox"/> (19) Machinist <input type="checkbox"/> (20) Medical laboratory scientist <input type="checkbox"/> (21) Midwife <input type="checkbox"/> (22) Nurse <input type="checkbox"/> (23) Officer/Employee <input type="checkbox"/> (24) Pharmacist <input type="checkbox"/> (25) Photographer <input type="checkbox"/> (26) Physician <input type="checkbox"/> (27) Plumber <input type="checkbox"/> (28) Programmer <input type="checkbox"/> (29) Radiographer <input type="checkbox"/> (30) Retiree <input type="checkbox"/> (31) Student <input type="checkbox"/> (32) Surveyor <input type="checkbox"/> (33) Tailor <input type="checkbox"/> (34) Teacher <input type="checkbox"/> (35) Technician <input type="checkbox"/> (36) Tradesman <input type="checkbox"/> (37) Welder <input type="checkbox"/> (98) None (Home) <input type="checkbox"/> (99) Unknown
Marital status	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Single <input type="checkbox"/> (2) Married <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Windowed <input type="checkbox"/> (4) Sexual experimented <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Social security status	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Paying patient <input type="checkbox"/> (2) National security fund (BS2) <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Health Equity Fund (indigent) <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown

Risk factors (patient form)

Nb. of children	__ __ (99 if Unknown)		
Tobacco use	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) Never smoked	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Currently smokes	<input type="checkbox"/> (2) Stopped smoking <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Alcohol consumption	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) Do not drink	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Drinks occasionally	<input type="checkbox"/> (2) Drinks regularly <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Oral contraception use	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) Never used	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Ever used	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Breast cancer history within the family	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) None	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) At least one	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Ovary cancer history within the family	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) None	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) At least one	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Other cancer history within the family	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) None	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) At least one	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown

Follow-up (patient form)

Date last contact	__ __ / __ __ / __ __ __ __ (DD/MM/YYYY)		
Relapse	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) No	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Yes, local relapse	<input type="checkbox"/> (2) Yes, distant relapse <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Yes, no precision <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Alive	<input type="checkbox"/> (2) Dead	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Date of death	__ __ / __ __ / __ __ __ __ (DD/MM/YYYY)		
Cause of death	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Cancer	<input type="checkbox"/> (2) Not cancer	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Cause if not cancer			

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Tumor form

If bilateral cancer, fill one tumor form for left breast and one for right breast. If multifocal cancer, fill one tumor form per tumor. If relapse/metastatic tumor, fill a new tumor form.

NCC Patient Nb.	
Tumor record Nb.	___

Patient (Tumor form)

Age at diagnosis	___ __ years old (99 if Unknown)
Address at diagnosis	Province/City: Srok/Khan: Khum/Sangkat:
Weight at diagnosis	___ __ __ kg (999 if Unknown)
Height at diagnosis	___ __ __ cm (999 if Unknown)
ECOG/WHO/Zubrod performance score	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) Asymptomatic <input type="checkbox"/> (1) Symptomatic but completely ambulatory <input type="checkbox"/> (2) Symptomatic, <50% in bed during the day <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Symptomatic, >50% in bed, but not bedbound <input type="checkbox"/> (4) Bedbound (completely disabled) <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Menopausal status at diagnosis	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Pre-menopausal <input type="checkbox"/> (2) Peri-menopausal <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Post-menopausal <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown

Tumor (Tumor form)

Tumor Type	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Primary <input type="checkbox"/> (2) Local relapse <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Metastasis		
Pathology Report Number (ANAPATH)			
Incidence Date / Date of diagnosis	___ __ / ___ __ / ___ __ __ __ (DD/MM/YYYY)		
Topography	<table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <input type="checkbox"/> (500) Nipple <input type="checkbox"/> (502) Upper-inner quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (504) Upper-outer quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (506) Axillary tail of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (509) Breast, NOS Other: _____ </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <input type="checkbox"/> (501) Central portion of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (503) Lower-inner quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (505) Lower-outer quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (508) Overl. lesion of breast </td> </tr> </table>	<input type="checkbox"/> (500) Nipple <input type="checkbox"/> (502) Upper-inner quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (504) Upper-outer quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (506) Axillary tail of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (509) Breast, NOS Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> (501) Central portion of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (503) Lower-inner quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (505) Lower-outer quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (508) Overl. lesion of breast
<input type="checkbox"/> (500) Nipple <input type="checkbox"/> (502) Upper-inner quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (504) Upper-outer quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (506) Axillary tail of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (509) Breast, NOS Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> (501) Central portion of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (503) Lower-inner quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (505) Lower-outer quadrant of breast <input type="checkbox"/> (508) Overl. lesion of breast		
Morphology	<table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Lobular carcinoma, NOS (8520) <input type="checkbox"/> Infiltrating duct and lobular carcinoma (8522) <input type="checkbox"/> Infiltrating lobular mixed with other types of (8524) <input type="checkbox"/> Neoplasm, malignant (8000) <input type="checkbox"/> Papillary carcinoma, NOS (8050) <input type="checkbox"/> Adenoid cystic carcinoma (8200) <input type="checkbox"/> Tubular adenocarcinoma (8211) <input type="checkbox"/> Papillary carcinoma, encapsulated (8343) <input type="checkbox"/> Mucinous adenocarcinoma (8480) <input type="checkbox"/> Secretory carcinoma of breast (8502) <input type="checkbox"/> Intracystic carcinoma, NOS (8504) <input type="checkbox"/> Medullary carcinoma with lymphoid stroma (8512) <input type="checkbox"/> Duct carcinoma, desmoplastic type (8514) <input type="checkbox"/> Paget disease, mammary (8540) </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Infiltrating ductular carcinoma (8521) <input type="checkbox"/> Infiltrating duct mixed with other types (8523) <input type="checkbox"/> Polymorph. low grade adenocarcinoma (8525) <input type="checkbox"/> Carcinoma, NOS (8010) <input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma, NOS (8140) <input type="checkbox"/> Cribriform carcinoma, NOS (8201) <input type="checkbox"/> Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS (8246) <input type="checkbox"/> Apocrine adenocarcinoma (8401) <input type="checkbox"/> Comedocarcinoma, NOS (8501) <input type="checkbox"/> Intraductal papillary adenoc. with inva (8503) <input type="checkbox"/> Medullary carcinoma, NOS (8510) <input type="checkbox"/> Atypical medullary carcinoma (8513) <input type="checkbox"/> Inflammatory carcinoma (8530) <input type="checkbox"/> Paget dis. and infiltrating duct carcin. (8541) </td> </tr> </table>	<input type="checkbox"/> Lobular carcinoma, NOS (8520) <input type="checkbox"/> Infiltrating duct and lobular carcinoma (8522) <input type="checkbox"/> Infiltrating lobular mixed with other types of (8524) <input type="checkbox"/> Neoplasm, malignant (8000) <input type="checkbox"/> Papillary carcinoma, NOS (8050) <input type="checkbox"/> Adenoid cystic carcinoma (8200) <input type="checkbox"/> Tubular adenocarcinoma (8211) <input type="checkbox"/> Papillary carcinoma, encapsulated (8343) <input type="checkbox"/> Mucinous adenocarcinoma (8480) <input type="checkbox"/> Secretory carcinoma of breast (8502) <input type="checkbox"/> Intracystic carcinoma, NOS (8504) <input type="checkbox"/> Medullary carcinoma with lymphoid stroma (8512) <input type="checkbox"/> Duct carcinoma, desmoplastic type (8514) <input type="checkbox"/> Paget disease, mammary (8540)	<input type="checkbox"/> Infiltrating ductular carcinoma (8521) <input type="checkbox"/> Infiltrating duct mixed with other types (8523) <input type="checkbox"/> Polymorph. low grade adenocarcinoma (8525) <input type="checkbox"/> Carcinoma, NOS (8010) <input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma, NOS (8140) <input type="checkbox"/> Cribriform carcinoma, NOS (8201) <input type="checkbox"/> Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS (8246) <input type="checkbox"/> Apocrine adenocarcinoma (8401) <input type="checkbox"/> Comedocarcinoma, NOS (8501) <input type="checkbox"/> Intraductal papillary adenoc. with inva (8503) <input type="checkbox"/> Medullary carcinoma, NOS (8510) <input type="checkbox"/> Atypical medullary carcinoma (8513) <input type="checkbox"/> Inflammatory carcinoma (8530) <input type="checkbox"/> Paget dis. and infiltrating duct carcin. (8541)
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Paget disease and intraductal carcin. of bre (8543) <input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma with squamous metaplasia (8570) <input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma with spindle cell metaplasia (8572) <input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentia (8574) <input type="checkbox"/> Angiomyosarcoma (8894) Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenosquamous carcinoma (8560) <input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcin. w cartilaginous & osseous (8571) <input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma with apocrine metaplasia (8573) <input type="checkbox"/> Metaplastic carcinoma, NOS (8575) <input type="checkbox"/> Phyllodes tumor, malignant (9020)
Behaviour	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) Benign <input type="checkbox"/> (2) In situ	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Uncertain <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Malignant
Grade	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) 1 <input type="checkbox"/> (2) 2 <input type="checkbox"/> (3) 3	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Lymphovascular invasion	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) No <input type="checkbox"/> (1) Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Additional in-situ	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) No <input type="checkbox"/> (1) Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
ER (Estrogen recept.)	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) Negative <input type="checkbox"/> (1) Positive	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
PR (Progesterone r.)	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) Negative <input type="checkbox"/> (1) Positive	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
HER2	<input type="checkbox"/> (00) None <input type="checkbox"/> (20) 2+ (amplification unknown) <input type="checkbox"/> (22) 2+ amplified	<input type="checkbox"/> (10) 1+ <input type="checkbox"/> (21) 2+ not amplified <input type="checkbox"/> (30) 3+ <input type="checkbox"/> (99) Unknown
Ki67 (in %)	___ __ % (999 if Unknown)	
Basis diagnosis	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) Death certificate only <input type="checkbox"/> (2) Clin. Investigation / Ult Soun <input type="checkbox"/> (4) Laboratory test <input type="checkbox"/> (6) Histology of metastase <input type="checkbox"/> (8) Autopsy / Histology	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Clinical only <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Surgery / Autopsy <input type="checkbox"/> (5) Cytology <input type="checkbox"/> (7) Histology of primary <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Extent	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) In situ <input type="checkbox"/> (2) Regional by direct extension <input type="checkbox"/> (4) Regional by both direct extension and lymph nodes involvement <input type="checkbox"/> (5) Regional, NOS	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Localized <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Regional lymph nodes only <input type="checkbox"/> (6) Distant <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Laterality	<input type="checkbox"/> (1) Left <input type="checkbox"/> (2) Right	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Bilaterality	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) Unilateral <input type="checkbox"/> (1) Bilateral	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Multifocality	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) Unifocal <input type="checkbox"/> (1) Multifocal	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
TNM (text resume)		
cT	<input type="checkbox"/> (01) T0 <input type="checkbox"/> (11) T1A <input type="checkbox"/> (12) T1B <input type="checkbox"/> (13) T1C <input type="checkbox"/> (20) T2 <input type="checkbox"/> (30) T3 <input type="checkbox"/> (41) T4A <input type="checkbox"/> (42) T4B <input type="checkbox"/> (43) T4C <input type="checkbox"/> (44) T4D <input type="checkbox"/> (99) Unknown	
cN	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) N0 <input type="checkbox"/> (1) N1 [1-3 or ipsilateral mobile lymph nodes] <input type="checkbox"/> (2) N2 [4-9 or ipsilateral fixed lymph nodes] <input type="checkbox"/> (3) N3 [10+ or ipsilateral supraclavicular nodes]	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
cM	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) M0 <input type="checkbox"/> (1) M1	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
pTNM or ypTNM?	<input type="checkbox"/> pTNM <input type="checkbox"/> ypTNM (neo-adjuvant)	
pT / ypT	<input type="checkbox"/> (01) T0 <input type="checkbox"/> (02) Tis <input type="checkbox"/> (11) T1A <input type="checkbox"/> (12) T1B <input type="checkbox"/> (13) T1C <input type="checkbox"/> (20) T2 <input type="checkbox"/> (30) T3 <input type="checkbox"/> (41) T4A <input type="checkbox"/> (42) T4B <input type="checkbox"/> (43) T4C <input type="checkbox"/> (44) T4D <input type="checkbox"/> (99) Unknown	
pN / ypN	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) N0 <input type="checkbox"/> (1) N1 [1-3] <input type="checkbox"/> (2) N2 [4-9] <input type="checkbox"/> (3) N3 [10+]	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
pM / ypM	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) M0 <input type="checkbox"/> (1) M1	<input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown

Immunotherapy start date	___ / ___ / _____ (DD/MM/YYYY)
Immunotherapy stop date	___ / ___ / _____ (DD/MM/YYYY)
Radiotherapy type	<input type="checkbox"/> (0) No radiotherapy done <input type="checkbox"/> (1) Breast only <input type="checkbox"/> (2) Breast + Lymph nodes <input type="checkbox"/> (3) Chest wall only <input type="checkbox"/> (4) Chest wall + Lymph nodes <input type="checkbox"/> (5) Metastasis <input type="checkbox"/> (9) Unknown
Radiotherapy start date	___ / ___ / _____ (DD/MM/YYYY)
Radiotherapy stop date	___ / ___ / _____ (DD/MM/YYYY)

Source 1 (Source form)

Source	<input type="checkbox"/> (01) Abroad <input type="checkbox"/> (02) Calmette Hospital <input type="checkbox"/> (03) Khmer-Soviet Hospital <input type="checkbox"/> (04) Kunthak Bopha H. <input type="checkbox"/> (05) Preah Angdoug Hospital <input type="checkbox"/> (06) Preah Ketomealea Hospital <input type="checkbox"/> (07) Preah Kosamak H. <input type="checkbox"/> (08) Province Hospital <input type="checkbox"/> (99) Unknown
Prov. hospital / Country	
Date of source	___ / ___ / _____ (DD/MM/YYYY)
Unit	<input type="checkbox"/> (01) Cardiology <input type="checkbox"/> (02) Dermatology <input type="checkbox"/> (03) E.N.T (O.R.L.) <input type="checkbox"/> (04) Emergency Department (Urgence Porte) <input type="checkbox"/> (05) Gynaecology <input type="checkbox"/> (06) ICU <input type="checkbox"/> (07) Internal Medicine <input type="checkbox"/> (08) Internal Medicine A <input type="checkbox"/> (09) Internal Med. A4 <input type="checkbox"/> (10) Internal Med. A5 <input type="checkbox"/> (11) Internal Medicine B <input type="checkbox"/> (12) Maternity <input type="checkbox"/> (13) Medical Neurology <input type="checkbox"/> (14) National Cancer Center <input type="checkbox"/> (15) Neonatal <input type="checkbox"/> (16) Nephrology (Hémodialyse) <input type="checkbox"/> (17) Oncology-Hematology <input type="checkbox"/> (18) OPD Unit (Consultation Externe) <input type="checkbox"/> (19) Ophthalmology <input type="checkbox"/> (20) Orthopaedic <input type="checkbox"/> (21) Radiology <input type="checkbox"/> (22) Surgery A <input type="checkbox"/> (23) Surgery B <input type="checkbox"/> (24) Surgery Neurology <input type="checkbox"/> (25) Urology <input type="checkbox"/> (26) Other <input type="checkbox"/> (99) Unknown
Path lab n°	
Case n°	

Source 2 (Source form)

Source	<input type="checkbox"/> (01) Abroad <input type="checkbox"/> (02) Calmette Hospital <input type="checkbox"/> (03) Khmer-Soviet Hospital <input type="checkbox"/> (04) Kunthak Bopha H. <input type="checkbox"/> (05) Preah Angdoug Hospital <input type="checkbox"/> (06) Preah Ketomealea Hospital <input type="checkbox"/> (07) Preah Kosamak H. <input type="checkbox"/> (08) Province Hospital <input type="checkbox"/> (99) Unknown
Prov. hospital / Country	
Date of source	___ / ___ / _____ (DD/MM/YYYY)
Unit	<input type="checkbox"/> (01) Cardiology <input type="checkbox"/> (02) Dermatology <input type="checkbox"/> (03) E.N.T (O.R.L.) <input type="checkbox"/> (04) Emergency Department (Urgence Porte) <input type="checkbox"/> (05) Gynaecology <input type="checkbox"/> (06) ICU <input type="checkbox"/> (07) Internal Medicine <input type="checkbox"/> (08) Internal Medicine A <input type="checkbox"/> (09) Internal Med. A4 <input type="checkbox"/> (10) Internal Med. A5 <input type="checkbox"/> (11) Internal Medicine B <input type="checkbox"/> (12) Maternity <input type="checkbox"/> (13) Medical Neurology <input type="checkbox"/> (14) National Cancer Center <input type="checkbox"/> (15) Neonatal <input type="checkbox"/> (16) Nephrology (Hémodialyse) <input type="checkbox"/> (17) Oncology-Hematology <input type="checkbox"/> (18) OPD Unit (Consultation Externe) <input type="checkbox"/> (19) Ophthalmology <input type="checkbox"/> (20) Orthopaedic <input type="checkbox"/> (21) Radiology <input type="checkbox"/> (22) Surgery A <input type="checkbox"/> (23) Surgery B <input type="checkbox"/> (24) Surgery Neurology <input type="checkbox"/> (25) Urology <input type="checkbox"/> (26) Other <input type="checkbox"/> (99) Unknown
Path lab n°	
Case n°	